

Spectrophotometric determination of saccharin in food and pharmaceutical products

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Manuscript received 12 September 1997, revised 3 February 1998, accepted 21 May 1998

A simple and highly sensitive method is described for the spectrophotometric determination of saccharin. The method is based on the bromination of saccharin to form *N*-bromo derivative, which reacts with potassium iodide to liberate iodine. The iodine liberated is then reacted with leuco crystal violet and the crystal violet dye formed shows λ_{\max} at 593 nm. The colour system obeys Beer's law in the range 0.05–0.5 $\mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$ of saccharin and has apparent molar absorptivity of $2.93 \times 10^5 \text{ dm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}$. The method is free from interference of common diverse ions and many of the ingredients commonly found in food products and has been satisfactorily applied to the determination of saccharin in food and pharmaceuticals.

The artificial sweetener saccharin is a weak bladder carcinogen and causes risk to human and animals¹. There are numerous instrumental method for the determination of saccharin in food, beverages and pharmaceuticals². Azure B³, phenothiazine⁴, feroin⁵, phenol-sulphuric acid⁶ and starch-CDI₂⁷ are the common reagents for spectrophotometric determination of saccharin, but many suffer from several drawbacks.

Here a simple and sensitive method for the spectrophotometric determination of saccharin is proposed with leucocrystal violet (LCV). This method has been applied to the determination of saccharin in food and pharmaceuticals.

Results and Discussion

The absorption spectra of crystal violet dye formed in the proposed reaction shows maximum λ_{\max} at 593 nm. The reagent blank gives negligible absorbance at this wavelength. The colour system obeys Beer's law over the range 1.25–12.5 μg of saccharin per 25 ml of final solution (0.05–0.5 ppm) at 593 nm. The molar absorptivity and Sandell's sensitivity were found to be $2.93 \times 10^5 \text{ dm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}$ and 0.0006 $\mu\text{g cm}^{-2}$ respectively.

Constant and maximum absorbance value were obtained when 0.5 ml of bromine water, 1 ml KI, 1 ml of LCV and 4–5 drops of 1 M NaOH were used. A few drops of formic acid were sufficient for the removal of excess bromine. It was found that ~2 min was sufficient for bromination and iodine was liberated on addition of KI immediately. Full colour development required ~15 min. Once developed the colour was found to be stable for several days. 55–65° temperature was found to be most suitable for colour reaction. pH range 4.5–5.5 was found to be optimum.

The validity of the method was assessed by investigating the effect of common foreign species added to a solu-

tion containing 10 μg per 25 ml of saccharin. Table 1 shows that saccharin can be selectively determined in presence of many substances that are likely to be present in different varieties of samples.

Table 1. Determination of saccharin in various samples*

Samples	Saccharin found** (μg)		% Recovery	
	P	R	P	R
Soft drinks ^a				
A	4.94 (± 0.020)	4.73	–	–
B	5.41 (± 0.025)	5.10	–	–
C	3.07 (± 0.021)	2.16	–	–
Ice-cream ^b				
A	6.56 (± 0.017)	6.25	–	–
B	6.61 (± 0.020)	6.45	–	–
C	6.09 (± 0.023)	5.88	–	–
Condensed milk ^b	10.05 (± 0.035)	9.89	–	–
Jam ^b	6.77 (± 0.020)	6.71	–	–
Toothpaste ^b				
A	8.64 (± 0.011)	8.48	–	–
B	8.12 (± 0.020)	8.02	–	–
C	8.75 (± 0.020)	8.54	–	–
Icing sugar ^{b,c}	9.73 (± 0.020)	9.53	97.30	95.30
Apple juice ^{a,c}	9.58 (± 0.030)	9.52	95.80	95.20
Orange juice ^{a,c}	9.68 (± 0.011)	9.60	96.80	96.00
Grape juice ^{a,c}	9.73 (± 0.017)	9.65	97.30	96.50
Tablet ^d				
A (12.00) ^e	11.80 (1.66%)	11.60	–	–
B (51.50) ^e	51.20 (0.58%)	51.00	–	–
C (12.50) ^e	12.40 (0.83%)	12.30	–	–

*P = Proposed method; R = reported method (Ref. 6).

**Mean of three replicate analysis.

^a10 ml of sample was treated as described in the procedure and then 1 ml of aliquot was analysed.

^b1 g of sample was treated as described in the procedure and then 1 ml of aliquot was analysed.

^cIn the saccharin free samples 10 μg of saccharin was added.

^dmg/tablet; R = reported method (Ref. 8).

^eClaimed value of a tablet (in mg/tablet).

Most of the common ions did not interfere in the procedure. The tolerance limits (ppm) of foreign species causing $\pm 2\%$ error in absorbance value were as follows: ascorbic acid (80); citric acid (500); tartaric acid (600); gelatine (750); sodium bicarbonate (850); benzoic acid (1000); malic acid (1500); sucrose (3000); glucose (4000); Co^{II} , Cu^{II} (400); Cr^{III} , Al^{III} , Zn^{II} , Be^{II} , Fe^{III} (850); phosphate, acetate, sulphate (2500); Ca^{II} (4000).

It can be concluded that the proposed method is simple, rapid, accurate and reproducible. The method has been compared favourably with most of the other methods and found to be sensitive and selective (Table 2).

Table 2. Comparison with other spectrophotometric methods

Method	λ_{max} nm	Detection limit ppm	Remarks
Phenol-sulphuric acid ^a	575	0.4	Long waiting time (2 h), corrosive reagent, less sensitive
Azure B ^b	685	2-68	Less sensitive
Phenothiazine ^c	510	20-400	Less sensitive, selective
Starch- CdI_2 ^d	600	0.4-1.6	Less sensitive
Proposed method	593	0.05-0.5	Sensitive, free from most of the interference

^aRef. 6. ^bRef. 3. ^cRef. 4. ^dRef. 7.

Experimental

A Systronics 108 UV-Vis spectrophotometer and a Systronics 331 pH meter were used.

A 1% stock solution of saccharin was prepared in double-distilled deionized water and standardized gravimetrically⁸. A saturated aqueous solution of bromine was prepared. Solutions of KI (0.1%; Merck), acetic acid (50%) and NaOH (1 M; Merck) were prepared in water. Solution of leuco crystal violet (Eastman Kodak) was prepared by shaking LCV (200 mg) in 85% phosphoric acid (3 ml) and shaken gently till the dye dissolved, and then diluted to 1 dm³ with water.

All chemicals used were of A.R. grade. Double-distilled deionized water was used for preparing solutions.

Calibration curve: An aliquot of working standard solution containing 1.25-12.5 μg of saccharin was taken in 25 ml calibrated tubes. To it bromine water (0.5 ml) was added and the mixture was shaken gently for 2 min. The excess bromine was then removed by dropwise addition of formic acid⁹ and then KI (1 ml) was added. The resulting yellow solution was shaken for a few seconds, followed by addition of LCV solution (1 ml) and 1 M NaOH (4-5 drops). The solution was kept in a thermostat (55°) for 5 min, then cooled, diluted to 25 ml with deionized water, kept for 10 min for full colour development and the absorbance measured at 593 nm against a reagent blank.

Soft drinks: Samples of different soft drinks were decarbonated by repeated shaking and pouring from one beaker to another. To the sample solution (10 ml) was added H_2SO_4 (1 ml; 10%) and the mixture was equilibrated with diethyl ether (2 \times 6 ml). The upper ether layer was equilibrated with 2% NaHCO_3 solution (2 \times 2 ml). The

ether layer was discarded and the aqueous layer was acidified with 5% HCl (2 ml) and extracted with diethyl ether (2 \times 5 ml). The ether was evaporated from the extract on a hot water-bath. The saccharin residue was dissolved in water (10 ml), made up to 25 ml with water³ and analysed as described above.

Jam, condensed milk and ice-cream: Each of the sample (1g) was dissolved in water (10 ml), deproteinised by adding 25% lead acetate¹⁰, acidified with 5% HCl (2 ml) and extracted with diethyl ether (3 \times 6 ml). The ethereal solution was then washed with water (5 ml). The ether layer was separated and evaporated on a hot water-bath. The residue was dissolved in water (10 ml), the volume made up to 25 ml¹⁰ and analysed as described above.

Pharmaceuticals: A saccharin tablet (purchased from the local pharmacy) was ground, weighed and stirred for 2-3 min with deionized water (50 ml), then 5% EDTA (1 ml) was added and the solution filtered. The insoluble mass was washed with water (3 \times 5 ml). The filtrate plus washing were diluted to 250 ml³. A known volume was further diluted depending upon the saccharin content and the colour of the sample. Aliquots were then analysed as described above.

Cosmetic samples: The samples of tooth paste (1 g of each) was dissolved in hot water (25 ml). The solution was cooled and centrifuged (1850 g) for 5 min. The supernatant solution was acidified with 10% HCl and saccharin extracted into ethyl acetate (3 \times 6 ml). The combined extracts was evaporated to dryness, the residue dissolved in water¹¹ (25 ml) and then analysed as described above.

Acknowledgement

The authors are thankful to Pt. Ravishankar Shukla University, Raipur, for facilities. One of the authors (J.V.D.) is thankful to C.S.I.R., New Delhi, for providing a Research Fellowship and the other (O.A.) to Pt. Ravishankar Shukla University, Raipur, for financial assistance.

References

1. R. Doll and R. Peto, *J. Nat. Cancer Inst.*, 1981, **66**, 1191.
2. Z. E. Viduad, R. Gariad and M. O. Gonzales, *E. Nahrung*, 1987, **31**, 105, 108 (*Anal. Abstr.*, 1987, **49**, 10F16); N. Katsuhika, K. Naoyoshi and T. Tsuyoshi *Nippon Shokuhin Kogyo Gakkaishi*, 1981, **28**, 321 (*Anal. Abstr.*, 1982, **43**, 2F21); R. C. Rooney and D. L. James, *Electroplat. Met. Finish*, 1964, **17**, 149; F. F. Orlandola and A. N. Joaquim, *Talanta*, 1994, **41**, 731.
3. P. G. Ramappa and A. Nayak, *Analyst*, 1963, **108**, 966.
4. A. Tanaka, N. Nose, T. Suzuki, S. Kobayashi and A. Watanoba, *Analyst*, 1977, **102**, 367.
5. E. C. Roy, E. L. Sayed and A. K. Yacoub, *Analyst*, 1982, **107**, 414.
6. K. Helrich, "Official Methods of Analysis", 15th ed., AOAC Inc. ("Food Composition, Additives, Natural Contaminants"), 1990, Vol. II, 1172; K. W. Chin and H. F. Chang, *Anal. Abstr.*, 1982, **43**, 2F3.
7. F. I. Khattab, *Anal. Lett.*, 1983, **16**, 1121.
8. P. M. Parikh and S. P. Mukherji, *Analyst*, 1960, **85**, 25.
9. M. Rai, K. N. Ramachandran and V. K. Gupta, *Analyst*, 1994, **119**, 1883.
10. E. G. Whittle, *Analyst*, 1944, **69**, 45.
11. H. Piekacz, E. Kiss and R. Pantow, *Zakl-Hig.*, 1983, **34**, 285 (*Anal. Abstr.*, 1984, **46**, 5C95).